

THE PROBLEM OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY IN THE ORGANIZATION OF
EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN GENERAL
EDUCATION SCHOOLS

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Abstract: This article discusses the issue of innovative activity, innovative technology processes, principles of pedagogical technology in the organization of education in general education schools on the basis of information technology, and their scientific theoretical analysis is made.

Key words: Pedagogical technology, innovative activity, technical tool, didactic, pedagogical, theory, reproductive method, etc.

- *Innovative activity - the need to acquire theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications based on directing the mental, mental and physical strength of the pedagogue to a specific goal, supplementing practical activities with theoretical knowledge, developing knowledge, design, communicative speech and organizational skills is enough.*
- *Specific signs of innovative activity include:*
 - *- striving to master the philosophy of creative activity;*
 - *- acquisition of pedagogical research methods;*
 - *- ability to create author's concepts;*
 - *- planning and practical application of experimental works;*
 - *- to be able to use the experiences of other researchers-pedagogues;*
 - *- establish cooperation with colleagues;*
 - *- to be able to exchange ideas and provide methodical assistance;*
 - *- prevention of difficulties and their elimination;*
 - *- to search for news and adapt them to one's own conditions.*
- *Pedagogical technology theory is a form of techno-pedagogical knowledge that scientifically and logically explains the laws of pedagogical activity and existing relationships through images and explanations. Understanding the essence of pedagogical technology, considering its structural structure, goals and objectives, and structures, as well as allows understanding the content of a group of basic concepts and categories. Pedagogical technology is scientifically based in accordance with time allocation and a clearly defined system of tasks of all stages and parts of the pedagogical process that ensures the achievement of the expected result.*
- *Innovative activities of teachers include:*
 - *- readiness to use the innovation;*
 - *- acceptance of pedagogical innovations;*
 - *- level of innovation;*
 - *- development of communication skills;*
 - *- creativity.*
- *The main goal of pedagogical technologies is to activate the educational process and achieve a high level of mastery of the material by students, and to teach students to think*

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independently and express their opinion. It is known that any pedagogical technology should be based on new principles that contribute to the development of education and should serve to form the student's personality. Therefore, in the center of modern pedagogical technology are the leader of the educational process and the teacher and students who are the subject and object of this process. For this, the requirements for the educational process, the principles of education organization and management, and the correct and clear organization of the student's personal activities, to enter into a proper dialogue with them, to solve problems and disagreements. It should include methods of timely elimination, creation of a creative working environment in the auditorium, clear and transparent assessment of students' activities.

- *Pedagogical innovation should remain the property of mass experiences. Pedagogical innovation is initially introduced into the work of some teachers. At the next stage, after testing and receiving an objective assessment, the pedagogical innovation is recommended for mass implementation.*
- *All processes of innovative technologies can be divided into:*
 - *The stage of searching for new ideas;*
 - *Stage of creation of news;*
 - *Implementation of news entry;*
 - *Reinforcement of news.*

Pedagogical technology principles

- types:
- Current traditional education,
 - Pedagogical technologies based on a person-oriented pedagogical process;
 - Pedagogical technologies based on activation and acceleration of students' activities;
 - Pedagogical technologies based on the efficiency of management and organization of the educational process;
 - Pedagogical technologies based on didactic improvement and reconstruction of the material;

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- Pedagogical technologies of special subjects;
- Alternative technologies;
- Technologies adapted to nature;
- Developing educational technologies;
- Pedagogical technologies of authorship schools;
- Technology design and development technologies.

Types of pedagogical technologies for managing cognitive activity:

- Classical lecture;
- Teaching with the help of technical means;
- Advisory system;
- Labor system;
- Teaching according to the textbook;
- System of small groups;
- Computer-aided teaching;
- Tutoring system;
- Programmable control.

Pedagogical technologies are classified according to the following characteristics:

- According to the level of application;
- According to the philosophical basis;
- According to the main development factor;
- According to the characteristics of the content;
- Approach to the child;
- By categories of learners.

According to the main method used, pedagogical technologies are divided into the following types:

- Dogmatic, reproductive method;
- Explanation, demonstration;
- Developmental education;
- Problematic, inquisitive;
- Creative method;

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- Programmed educational method;
- Dialogue method;
- Game method;
- Self-developing educational method;
- Method of informed education.

According to the type of approach to the learner, pedagogical technologies are named as follows:

- Authoritarian;
- Didactic oriented;
- Socially oriented;
- Anthropologically oriented;
- Pedagogically oriented;
- Person-oriented;
- Focused on cooperation technologies;
- Focused on free education;
- Oriented to esoteric education and training.

Pedagogical technologies are divided into the following types based on their orientation to the characteristics and qualities of a person:

- Focused on the formation of knowledge and skills in subjects - information technologies;
- Operational technologies aimed at forming methods of mental activity;
- Emotional-artistic and emotional moral technologies aimed at forming the field of aesthetic and moral relations;
- Self-development technologies aimed at forming personal self-development mechanisms;
- Heuristic technologies aimed at developing creative abilities;
- Applied technologies aimed at developing the field of practical activity.

It is worth noting that the following conclusion can be made about the specific nature of the use of information technologies in the teaching of social and humanitarian sciences in general education schools; the educational process is activated, a high level of mastery of educational materials is achieved by students, positive results are achieved in students' independent thinking and free expression of their opinion.

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